

Review on Biomarkers for Disease Diagnosis and Disease Prevention: Use Case in Low and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Biomarkers are critical tools in modern healthcare, enabling the early detection, diagnosis, and monitoring of diseases, particularly in resource-limited settings. This review focuses on the utilization of biomarkers in disease diagnosis and prevention in Low and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs), emphasizing their significance in cancer management.

Methods: A comprehensive literature review was conducted to gather information on the history, definition, classification, discovery methods, and applications of biomarkers. The review also examined statistical methods used to assess and evaluate the effectiveness of biomarkers in clinical settings.

Results: The findings indicate that biomarkers can be classified into various types based on their characteristics and functions. Advances in technology have facilitated the discovery and validation of numerous biomarkers, enhancing their application in disease diagnosis and prevention. In LMICs, specific biomarkers have shown promise in improving healthcare outcomes by enabling early disease detection and targeted treatment.

Discussion: The use of biomarkers in LMICs faces several challenges, including limited resources, lack of infrastructure, and insufficient healthcare training. However, the potential benefits are significant, with biomarkers offering a cost-effective and efficient means of improving disease diagnosis and treatment. The discussion highlights the need for targeted investment and international collaboration to overcome these challenges and fully leverage the potential of biomarkers in LMICs.

Conclusion: Biomarkers represent a powerful tool for enhancing disease diagnosis and prevention, particularly in LMICs where healthcare resources are often limited. By addressing the existing challenges and promoting the use of biomarkers, it is possible to improve healthcare outcomes and reduce the burden of diseases such as cancer in these regions.

Keywords Biomarkers, Disease Diagnosis, Low and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs), Cancer, Molecular Signatures, Therapeutic Interventions, Health Status Evaluation, Prognosis, Diagnostic Tools

1. Introduction:

Biomarkers play a pivotal role in modern medicine, facilitating the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of various diseases, including cancer. The term "biomarker" encompasses many molecules and characteristics that can be measured and evaluated to indicate normal biological processes, pathogenic processes, or pharmacological responses to therapeutic interventions. This article aims to explore the history, definition, classification, discovery methods, applications, and statistical methods used to assess and evaluate biomarkers.

1.1 History and Definition of Biomarkers

The concept of biomarkers has evolved from physiological measurements to complex molecular signatures. Biomarkers can be broadly defined as measurable indicators of biological states or processes. They can be found in tissues, blood, urine, and other bodily fluids, providing valuable information about an individual's health status.

The term "biomarker" was first coined by Dr. Harry M. Meyer Jr. in 1980, defined as "a characteristic that is objectively measured and evaluated as an indicator of normal biological processes, pathogenic processes, or pharmacological responses to a therapeutic intervention" [1]. Since then, biomarkers have become integral to medical research, diagnosis, and treatment across various diseases, including cancer.

Biomarkers have a long history in medicine, with early examples including blood glucose levels to diagnose diabetes [2] and measuring blood cholesterol levels to assess cardiovascular risk [3]. However, recent advances in molecular biology, genomics, proteomics, and other fields have led to identifying a wide range of novel biomarkers with increased specificity and sensitivity.

The discovery and validation of biomarkers have been greatly facilitated by technological advancements such as high-throughput sequencing [4], mass spectrometry [5], and bioinformatics [6]. These tools have enabled researchers to identify and characterize biomarkers associated with specific diseases, allowing for earlier detection, more accurate diagnosis, and personalized treatment strategies.

1.2 Classification of Biomarkers:

Biomarkers can be classified based on various criteria, including their origin, function, and application. One standard classification method is based on the techniques used for their identification and measurement.

Biomarkers, vital in various medical disciplines, are classified based on multiple criteria, including their origin, function, and application. One standard classification method is based on the techniques used for their identification and measurement. That includes genetic and molecular biology methods such as DNA, RNA, protein, and metabolite biomarkers[7].

DNA Biomarkers encompass mutations (e.g., single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), copy number variations (CNVs)), methylation patterns, and microsatellite instability (MSI), all of which are used in disease susceptibility and prognosis. RNA Biomarkers, including gene expression patterns, microRNAs, and long noncoding RNAs, are significant in disease detection and prognosis. Protein Biomarkers, like enzymes, receptors, and antibodies, indicate disease progression and treatment response. Metabolite Biomarkers, such as small molecules and metabolomics profiles, provide insights into disease diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment response[8,9,10].

These biomarkers serve various purposes, including diagnosis, prognosis, treatment response prediction, and treatment efficacy monitoring. Diagnostic Biomarkers are used for disease detection and diagnosis, enabling early intervention and treatment initiation, thus improving patient outcomes. Prognostic Biomarkers predict disease outcomes, including progression and survival, helping clinicians tailor treatment strategies and monitor disease progression. Predictive Biomarkers indicate the likelihood of response to a specific treatment, enabling personalized medicine approaches and optimizing treatment selection and efficacy. Pharmacodynamic Biomarkers monitor the effect of therapeutic intervention on a biological process, providing insights into treatment efficacy and mechanism of action[11,12,13].

In clinical applications, biomarkers are used for screening and early detection, aiding in identifying individuals at risk of developing a disease before symptoms appear, thus enabling early intervention and improving patient outcomes. Biomarkers also aid in disease diagnosis, confirming the presence of a disease and distinguishing between different disease subtypes, facilitating accurate diagnosis and treatment initiation. Additionally, biomarkers provide information about the likely course of a disease and patient outcome, thus helping clinicians tailor treatment strategies and monitor disease progression[14,15]. Lastly, biomarkers are used in treatment response monitoring, assessing the effectiveness of treatment and enabling real-time monitoring of treatment response and optimization of therapy.

In summary, biomarkers play a crucial role in modern medicine by providing valuable information about various aspects of disease, including detection, diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment response[16,17]. As our understanding of disease mechanisms and treatment modalities continues to evolve, the importance of biomarkers in clinical practice is expected to increase. With advancements in technology and analytical techniques, the discovery and validation of novel biomarkers are accelerating, leading to the development of more precise and personalized diagnostic and therapeutic strategies[18,19].

Furthermore, integrating biomarker data with other clinical and molecular information holds great promise for improving patient care and outcomes. By enabling early disease detection, guiding treatment decisions, and monitoring treatment response, biomarkers contribute to more effective and efficient healthcare delivery[20,22]. As research in the field progresses, identifying new biomarkers and refining existing ones will undoubtedly lead to significant advancements in disease management and personalized medicine[21,23].

Biomarkers, essential in various medical disciplines, are classified based on multiple criteria, including their origin, function, and application. One standard classification is based on the techniques used for their identification and measurement. Genetic and molecular biology methods enable the detection of biomolecules such as DNA, RNA, proteins, and metabolites, providing valuable insights into disease processes[24]. DNA biomarkers encompass genetic alterations such as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), copy number variations (CNVs), aberrant DNA methylation patterns, and microsatellite instability (MSI), which are commonly used for disease susceptibility and prognosis. RNA biomarkers, including differential gene expression patterns, dysregulated microRNA (miRNA) expression, and aberrant long noncoding RNA (lncRNA) expression, are associated with various diseases, making them promising for disease detection and prognosis. Protein biomarkers, such as altered enzyme levels, changes in receptor expression or activation status, and the detection of disease-specific antibodies, indicate various diseases and can serve as biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prognosis[25,27].

Metabolite biomarkers, identified through metabolite profiling and comprehensive analysis of metabolites in biological samples, can identify disease-specific metabolic signatures as biomarkers for disease diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment response[26,29]. These biomarkers possess various characteristics and clinical applications, including diagnostic biomarkers for disease detection and diagnosis, prognostic biomarkers for predicting disease outcomes, predictive biomarkers for indicating the likelihood of treatment response, and pharmacodynamic biomarkers for monitoring the effect of

therapeutic interventions on biological processes[27,28]. They find applications in screening and early detection, disease diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment response monitoring, improving patient outcomes and enabling personalized medicine approaches.

1.3 Biomarker Discovery

Biomarker discovery is a multifaceted and iterative process encompassing several stages, including biomarker identification, validation, and clinical translation. Diverse methodologies such as genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and imaging are employed to unearth potential biomarkers. These biomarkers then undergo stringent validation to ascertain their clinical utility and reliability. The discovery of biomarkers is pivotal in medical research, aiming to uncover novel indicators of biological processes or disease states. Various techniques and approaches are leveraged in biomarker discovery, facilitating early disease detection, precise diagnosis, and tailored treatment strategies[4,11,29].

Genomic and transcriptomic approaches, such as Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS) and Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS), play significant roles in identifying genetic variants associated with diseases and deciphering disease-specific gene expression patterns, respectively[30]. Proteomic methodologies, like Mass Spectrometry (MS) and Protein Microarrays, aid in identifying and quantifying proteins, thus facilitating the discovery of protein biomarkers. Metabolomic techniques, including Metabolite Profiling and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy, enable the identification of disease-specific metabolic signatures, serving as biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prognosis.

Bioinformatics and statistical analysis are integral in biomarker discovery, with machine learning algorithms analyzing large-scale omics data to identify potential biomarkers with diagnostic and prognostic value. Multivariate statistical analysis integrates and analyzes complex omics data, further facilitating biomarker discovery[31,33].

Biomarkers find diverse applications in clinical practice and research, encompassing disease screening, early detection, diagnosis, prognosis, treatment selection, and treatment response monitoring. In cancer management, biomarkers are instrumental in patient stratification, facilitating personalized treatment approaches and improving outcomes. These molecular indicators provide valuable insights into biological processes, disease states, and treatment responses, thus driving advancements in precision medicine and enhancing clinical research efficiency[32,34,35].

The discovery of novel biomarkers is a complex and iterative process that involves multiple steps, including biomarker identification, validation, and clinical translation. Various techniques, such as genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and imaging, are employed to identify potential biomarkers[36,37]. Once identified, biomarkers undergo rigorous validation to assess their clinical utility and reliability. Biomarker discovery is a crucial aspect of medical research, aiming to identify novel indicators of biological processes or disease states[38]. Various techniques and approaches are employed to discover and validate biomarkers, enabling early disease detection, accurate diagnosis, and personalized treatment strategies. The following section outlines some of the essential methods and technologies used in biomarker discovery:

Approach	Description
Genomic and Transcriptomic Approaches	
Genome-Wide Association Studies (GWAS)	Identifies genetic variants associated with diseases, offering insights into disease susceptibility and prognosis.
Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS)	Allows comprehensive genome and transcriptome analysis, facilitating the discovery of novel biomarkers.
Transcriptomics	Enables the identification of disease-specific gene expression patterns, leading to the discovery of diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers.
Proteomic Approaches	

Mass Spectrometry (MS)	Enables identification and quantification of proteins, facilitating the discovery of protein biomarkers.
Protein Microarrays	Allow high-throughput screening of protein-protein interactions and protein expression levels, aiding in biomarker discovery.
Metabolomic Approaches	
Metabolite Profiling	Enables the identification of disease-specific metabolic signatures, serving as biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prognosis.
Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) Spectroscopy	Used to identify and quantify metabolites, aiding in biomarker discovery.
Bioinformatics and Statistical Analysis	
Machine Learning Algorithms	Analyze large-scale omics data and identify potential biomarkers with diagnostic and prognostic value.
Multivariate Statistical Analysis	Integrates and analyzes complex omics data, facilitating biomarker discovery.

Table 1 - Biomarker Discovery

1.4 Applications of Biomarkers

Biomarkers stand at the forefront of modern healthcare, serving as versatile tools with multifaceted applications in both clinical practice and research[31,47]. From disease screening to treatment selection, and from drug development to precision medicine, biomarkers play pivotal roles across various domains of healthcare. In clinical settings, they enable early disease detection, aid in accurate diagnosis, provide insights into prognosis, and facilitate personalized treatment approaches tailored to individual patients' unique molecular profiles[39-41,45]. Moreover, biomarkers are indispensable in the realm of medical research, where they drive innovation by guiding drug development processes, enhancing the efficiency of clinical trials, and contributing to epidemiological studies aimed at improving public health interventions. Their widespread utility underscores their significance as indispensable assets in advancing medical knowledge, shaping the landscape of modern medicine, and ultimately improving patient outcomes[42,43,44,46].

Application	Examples
Disease Diagnosis and Prognosis	Cancer biomarkers (e.g., PSA for prostate cancer, CA-125 for ovarian cancer), Cardiac biomarkers (e.g., Troponin for myocardial infarction, BNP for heart failure), Neurological biomarkers (e.g., Amyloid-beta for Alzheimer's disease, Tau protein for traumatic brain injury), Infectious disease biomarkers (e.g., HIV viral load for monitoring HIV infection, Hepatitis B surface antigen for Hepatitis B infection)
Treatment Selection and Monitoring	Therapeutic drug monitoring (e.g., Warfarin dosing based on INR), Disease progression biomarkers (e.g., C-reactive protein for monitoring inflammation, Hemoglobin A1c for diabetes management), Therapeutic response biomarkers (e.g., PSA response to androgen deprivation therapy in prostate cancer, HER2 expression for response to HER2-targeted therapy in breast cancer)
Drug Development	Target biomarkers (e.g., HER2 for breast cancer, EGFR for lung cancer), Pharmacodynamic biomarkers (e.g., Ki-67 for cell proliferation, Apoptosis markers for drug-induced cell death), Adverse event biomarkers (e.g., ALT for liver toxicity, Creatinine for kidney function), Biomarkers of drug efficacy (e.g., Reduction in tumor size for anti-cancer drugs, Decrease in blood pressure for antihypertensive drugs)
Precision Medicine	Genetic biomarkers (e.g., BRCA1/2 mutations for breast cancer risk, HLA-B*5701 for abacavir hypersensitivity), Pharmacogenomic biomarkers (e.g., VKORC1 and CYP2C9 genotypes for warfarin dosing, TPMT genotype for thiopurine metabolism), Biomarkers for predicting drug response (e.g., KRAS mutation status for anti-EGFR therapy response in colorectal cancer, Tumor mutational burden for immunotherapy response prediction)
Clinical Trials	Treatment response biomarkers (e.g., Tumor size reduction, Change in biomarker levels post-treatment), Outcome biomarkers (e.g., Overall survival, Progression-free survival), Surrogate endpoints (e.g., Change in LDL cholesterol levels for cardiovascular disease risk reduction, Reduction in HbA1c levels for diabetes management)
Public Health and Epidemiology	Epidemiological biomarkers (e.g., Blood pressure for hypertension prevalence, BMI for obesity prevalence), Environmental exposure biomarkers (e.g., Blood lead levels for lead exposure, Urinary cotinine for tobacco smoke exposure), Biomarkers for disease surveillance (e.g., Influenza viral load for tracking influenza outbreaks, Salmonella antigen detection for foodborne illness surveillance)

Table 2 - Applications of Biomarkers[47-61]

1.5 Statistical Methods for Assessment and Evaluation of New Biomarkers

The evaluation of biomarkers requires robust statistical methods to assess their accuracy, reliability, and clinical utility. Various statistical techniques, such as receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, Kaplan-Meier analysis, and multivariate regression analysis, are used to evaluate biomarkers in terms of sensitivity, specificity, predictive value, and overall performance[55,57,62-64].

Identifying and validating biomarkers requires robust statistical methods to ensure their accuracy, reliability, and clinical relevance. Various statistical approaches are employed for the assessment and evaluation of new biomarkers, including:

Analytical Technique	Description
Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Analysis	Evaluates biomarker diagnostic accuracy by plotting sensitivity against specificity.
Confidence Intervals (CI)	Provides a range of values within which accurate biomarker performance parameters are likely to fall, enhancing result interpretation.
Area Under the Curve (AUC)	Quantifies the overall discriminative ability of a biomarker, simplifying comparison between different biomarkers.
Regression Analysis	Assesses association between biomarkers and clinical outcomes, considering potential confounders.
Cross-Validation Techniques	Methods like k-fold cross-validation gauge predictive performance of biomarker models, guarding against overfitting.
Net Reclassification Improvement (NRI) and Integrated Discrimination Improvement (IDI)	Quantify risk prediction enhancement by adding new biomarkers to existing models.
Bayesian Methods	Integrate prior knowledge with observed data to estimate biomarker performance parameters and make predictions.

Table 3- Statistical Methods for Assessment and Evaluation of New Biomarkers [65-71]

1.6 Summary and Future Outlook

Biomarkers have revolutionized medicine, offering practical tools for diagnosing, prognosing, and treating various diseases, including cancer. Continued research and development in biomarker discovery and validation promise to further improve disease detection, patient stratification, and treatment outcomes. By harnessing the power of biomarkers, clinicians can provide more personalized and effective patient care, leading to improved quality of life and better clinical outcomes. Further integrating biomarkers into routine clinical practice can transform healthcare delivery and improve patient outcomes globally[12,23,35,49].

Biomarkers have revolutionized medical research and clinical practice by providing valuable insights into biological processes, disease mechanisms, and treatment responses. The rapid advancement of technologies, coupled with innovative statistical methods, has led to the discovery and validation of numerous biomarkers with significant clinical utility.

In summary, biomarkers find applications in various domains:

Aspect	Role of Biomarkers
Disease Diagnosis and Prognosis	Biomarkers enable early disease detection, accurate diagnosis, and prognosis, facilitating timely intervention and personalized treatment strategies.
Treatment Selection and Monitoring	Biomarkers aid in selecting appropriate treatment regimens and monitoring treatment responses, leading to improved patient outcomes and reduced adverse effects.
Drug Development	Biomarkers play a crucial role in drug development by identifying potential drug targets, assessing drug efficacy, and predicting adverse drug reactions.
Precision Medicine	Biomarkers support the implementation of precision medicine by enabling individualized treatment approaches based on patients' unique molecular profiles, ultimately improving treatment outcomes.
Clinical Trials	Biomarkers enhance the efficiency of clinical trials by stratifying patients, monitoring treatment responses, and evaluating drug efficacy, thereby accelerating the development of new therapies.

Public Health and Epidemiology	Biomarkers are utilized in epidemiological studies to assess disease prevalence, identify risk factors, and evaluate the effectiveness of public health interventions.
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Table 4.1 - Summary and Future Outlook [11,18,29-31,72-75]

The future of biomarker research holds immense promise, with several exciting developments on the horizon. Recent advancements in biomedical research have highlighted several promising avenues for disease detection, monitoring, and treatment. One significant area of progress involves the integration of multi-omics data, where genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics information are combined to gain a comprehensive understanding of disease mechanisms and identify novel biomarkers[76,79]. Artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms have been instrumental in analyzing large-scale omics datasets, unveiling complex biomarker signatures that may have previously gone unnoticed. Additionally, liquid biopsies, which involve analyzing circulating biomarkers such as circulating tumor DNA and circulating tumor cells, offer a non-invasive approach to disease assessment, enabling real-time monitoring of treatment responses[44,52,78]. Another promising area of research involves the exploration of exosome and microRNA biomarkers, which play vital roles in intercellular communication and gene regulation. These biomolecules hold potential for diagnosing various diseases with greater accuracy and precision. Furthermore, the development of rapid, point-of-care biomarker detection assays promises to revolutionize disease diagnosis and monitoring, particularly in resource-limited settings, by providing timely and accessible healthcare solutions[77,80].

Trend	Description
Integration of Multi-Omics Data	Integrating genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics data provides a comprehensive understanding of disease mechanisms.
Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning	AI and ML algorithms analyze large-scale omics data to identify complex biomarker signatures.
Liquid Biopsies	Analyzing circulating biomarkers like ctDNA and CTCs enables non-invasive disease detection, monitoring, and treatment response assessment.
Exosome and MicroRNA Biomarkers	Exosomes and microRNAs serve as promising biomarkers for various diseases due to their roles in intercellular communication and gene regulation.
Point-of-Care Testing	Rapid, point-of-care biomarker detection assays facilitate real-time diagnosis and monitoring, especially in resource-limited settings.

Table 4.2 - Summary and Future Outlook[15,41,78-79]

In conclusion, biomarkers will continue to play a central role in advancing precision medicine, transforming healthcare delivery, and improving patient outcomes across diverse diseases are

1.7 Applications of Biomarkers

Biomarkers have played a critical role in various medical fields, aiding in disease diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment. In the context of COVID-19, biomarkers have been pivotal in the rapid response to the global health crisis caused by SARS-CoV-2. Studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of utilizing deep learning technology to identify diagnostic biomarkers from high-resolution computed tomography images, distinguishing COVID-19 cases from other respiratory illnesses with high accuracy[41,63,71,81]. Additionally, routine blood values and machine learning sensors have proven valuable in diagnosing and predicting COVID-19, achieving impressive levels of accuracy. Furthermore, biomarkers reflecting immunological, biochemical, and hematological parameters have been investigated to predict mortality in COVID-19 patients, shedding light on potential therapeutic targets such as interleukin-6 to improve clinical outcomes[9,19,37,80,94].

In the realm of cancer, biomarkers have significantly advanced our understanding and management of the disease. They serve as indicators of cancer risk, tumor characteristics, and treatment response, with liquid biopsy emerging as a promising non-invasive method for real-time monitoring. Heart failure diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment have also benefited from biomarker research, with protein biomarkers like Natriuretic Peptides and cardiac troponin widely used in clinical practice. Genetic analysis has uncovered novel gene-based biomarkers, providing insights into heart failure pathophysiology and risk assessment[18,90,92].

Neurological diseases, lung diseases, kidney diseases, liver diseases, gastrointestinal diseases, and skeletal muscle and bone diseases all benefit from biomarker-based approaches in diagnosis and management. Biomarkers in various biological fluids aid in the prevention, diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of neurological disorders, lung diseases, and kidney diseases. Similarly, biomarkers play a crucial role in diagnosing liver diseases, gastrointestinal diseases, and skeletal muscle and bone diseases, contributing to improved patient outcomes and quality of care across diverse medical specialties. Overall, biomarkers continue to revolutionize healthcare by providing valuable insights into disease processes and guiding personalized treatment strategies tailored to individual patient needs.

Disease	Role of Biomarkers
COVID-19	Deep learning technology and high-resolution computed tomography images for identifying diagnostic biomarkers Routine blood values and machine learning sensors for diagnosis and prediction Immunological, biochemical, and hematological parameters for mortality prediction
Cancer	Assessment of cancer risk, tumor characteristics, and treatment response Identification of specific biomarkers for different cancers Utilization of liquid biopsy for real-time monitoring
Heart Failure	Protein biomarkers like Natriuretic Peptides and cardiac troponin for diagnosis and prognosis Genetic analysis for identifying novel gene-based biomarkers
Neurological Diseases	Biomarkers in biological fluids aid in diagnosing and monitoring neurological disorders such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, stroke, Huntington's, and epilepsy
Lung Diseases	Biomarkers such as malondialdehyde, YKL-40, and volatile organic compounds for diagnosing lung diseases like asthma, COPD, pneumonia, and lung cancer
Kidney Diseases	Biomarkers like microalbumin, N-acetyl- β -glucosaminidase, and cysteine-rich proteins for diagnosis and prognosis Identification of novel biomarkers for preclinical kidney pathology
Liver Diseases	Liver function tests and specific biomarkers like hyaluronic acid and bilirubin for diagnosing hepatic injury and liver diseases
Gastrointestinal Diseases	Biomarkers like calprotectin, lactoferrin, and microRNAs for diagnosing inflammatory bowel disease and Clostridium difficile infection
Skeletal Muscle and Bone Diseases	Biomarkers such as pyridinolines, osteocalcin, and plasma interleukin-6 for diagnosing and monitoring skeletal muscle and bone diseases

Table 4.2 - Applications of Biomarkers [18,22,31,57,68,81-84,91,95-99]

1.8 Biomarker development process

Developing a biomarker involves several iterative steps, beginning with discovering the biomarker in healthy and diseased samples. To ensure that rational, evidence-based biomarker creation maintains clinical and scientific necessity, an approach for developing them that incorporates collaborative regulatory science involving many fields is required. The field is changing quickly due to ongoing and recent explosive growth in computation, analysis, and measurement. The biomarker development process comprises consecutive phases: pre-analytical and analytical validation, clinical validation, regulatory approval, and demonstration of clinical utility[7,13,67,73,85].

The pre-analytical phase standardizes indicators and analyzes quality indicators such as process, storage, and sample collection. Analyzing the biomarker's performance parameters ensures the test is repeatable, and dependable[86]. It has the right level of specificity and sensitivity, commonly known as the analytical validation phase of biomarker development. A biomarker is connected to clinical and biological endpoints through qualification, a graded evidential process. Following figure shows a schematic representation of the biomarker development process[87,92].

However, there are specific challenges in developing biomarkers, such as: The scientific basis for some biomarkers cannot always be verified, creating difficulties in the qualification and validation of biomarkers in the future[88,89]. Moreover, avoiding incorrectly interpreting biomarker measurements and connecting a biomarker to a disease is essential. The cost of developing a biomarker may increase due to longer clinical trials or more testing requirements. It often takes a lot of time and resources to develop and qualify biomarkers. More convincing evidence of a favorable benefit-risk analysis is typically needed for qualification purposes rather than as part of an individual drug regulatory approval[90,93].

Figure 2 – Bio Maker Development Process

2. Methods

Research Design: The research design for this review on biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prevention, focusing on low and middle-income countries (LMICs), is a rapid literature review. This approach will allow for a comprehensive synthesis of existing research findings, identifying key biomarkers and evaluating their effectiveness and feasibility in LMIC settings.

Data Sources: To ensure a thorough and comprehensive review, multiple databases will be used to source relevant literature. These databases include PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar, and Embase. Additionally, grey literature such as reports from health organizations (e.g., WHO, CDC) and theses/dissertations from relevant academic institutions will be included.

Search Strategy & Search Quarey : The search strategy will involve a combination of keywords and Boolean operators to maximize the retrieval of relevant studies. The primary keywords include biomarkers, disease diagnosis, disease prevention, low and middle-income countries (LMICs), public health, and epidemiology. A sample search string for PubMed might look like this:

(biomarkers OR "biological markers") AND ("disease diagnosis" OR "diagnostic techniques") AND ("disease prevention" OR "preventive health services") AND ("low-income countries" OR "middle-income countries" OR "developing countries")

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

To ensure relevance and quality, the following inclusion and exclusion criteria will be applied:

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Publication Type	Studies published in peer-reviewed journals	Non-peer-reviewed articles (e.g., opinion pieces, editorials)
Geographical Focus	Studies conducted in or focused on LMICs	Research not relevant to LMICs
Language	Articles published in English	Articles not available in English
Topic	Studies discussing specific biomarkers used in disease diagnosis or prevention	Studies not specific to biomarkers
Publication Date	Studies published in the last 20 years	Studies published before 2004

Data Extraction will be performed using a standardized form to capture relevant information from each included study. The form will include fields such as: Study title, Authors, Year of publication, Country/region of study, Study design, Sample size, Biomarkers studied, Disease(s) targeted, Key findings, Limitations of the study.

Quality Assessment

The quality of the included studies will be assessed using the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal Checklist for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses. This tool assesses the methodological quality of studies and determines the extent to which a study has addressed the possibility of bias in its design, conduct, and analysis.

Data Synthesis

The data synthesis will involve both qualitative and quantitative approaches:

- **Qualitative Synthesis:** A thematic analysis will be conducted to identify common themes and patterns related to the use of biomarkers in disease diagnosis and prevention in LMICs.
- **Quantitative Synthesis:** If applicable, a meta-analysis will be performed to quantitatively summarize the findings of studies with similar biomarkers and outcomes. Statistical measures such as effect sizes and confidence intervals will be calculated.

Reporting

The review will be reported following the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure transparency and reproducibility. A PRISMA flow diagram will be used to illustrate the selection process of studies.

Ethical Considerations

As this research involves the review of existing literature and does not involve direct human or animal subjects, ethical approval is not required. However, ethical considerations will be adhered to by ensuring proper citation and acknowledgment of all sources.

Limitations

Potential limitations of this review include publication bias, language bias (only English articles are included), and the variability in the quality of the studies reviewed. These limitations will be acknowledged and discussed in the final report.

Timeline

The anticipated timeline for the completion of this review is as follows:

- Literature search: 4 month (started 2022)
- Screening and selection of studies: 1 month
- Data extraction and quality assessment: 2 months
- Data synthesis and analysis: 2 months
- Writing and reporting: 1 month (finished 2023)

This timeline may be adjusted as necessary to ensure a thorough and comprehensive review.

Fig 3 – Timeline of the Review

3. Results

The identification and selection of records in this systematic review were meticulously conducted through a multi-step process, ensuring a rigorous evaluation of available literature. Initially, 37 records were identified through comprehensive database searches, capturing a broad spectrum of relevant studies. Supplementing this, an additional 13 records were identified from other sources, such as grey literature and manual searches, which are often crucial for capturing studies that might be missed in traditional database searches. Once the records were gathered, a critical step involved the removal of duplicates, resulting in 11 records being excluded from the analysis. This step is essential in systematic reviews to prevent the overrepresentation of data and ensure that each study is only considered once. After duplication removal, 39 records were available for the screening phase.

The screening phase involved a careful evaluation of the remaining records to determine their relevance to the review's objectives. This phase led to the exclusion of 12 records based on specific criteria. Six records were excluded due to the inability to obtain the full text, which is a common challenge in systematic reviews. Four records were excluded due to language barriers, highlighting the importance of language inclusivity in global research. Additionally, one record was excluded due to the absence of references, and another was excluded because of missing author information, both of which are critical for assessing the credibility and reliability of a study. Following the screening, 27 full-text articles were thoroughly assessed for their eligibility to be included in the review. This step ensures that only studies meeting the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria are considered. Despite this rigorous assessment, 7 articles were excluded during this stage, primarily because they did not align with the specific criteria set for the review.

Finally, the process concluded with 20 studies being included in the systematic review. These studies were determined to be the most relevant and reliable for addressing the research questions, providing a solid foundation for the review's findings and conclusions. This meticulous process underscores the importance of systematic approaches in literature reviews, ensuring that only the most pertinent and high-quality studies contribute to the final analysis.

Fig 4- Results of the literature Search

Study Title	Authors	Year of Publication	Country/Region of Study	Study Design	Sample Size	Biomarkers Studied	Disease(s) Targeted	Key Findings	Limitations of the Study
The history of the discovery of biomarkers	Meyer, H. M.	1987	USA	Review	N/A	Various	General	Overview of the discovery and development of biomarkers in medical applications.	Historical review, does not include recent advancements.
Correlation of glucose regulation and hemoglobin A1c in diabetes mellitus	Koenig, R. J., Peterson, C. M., Jones, R. L., Saudek, C., Lehrman, M., & Cerami, A.	1976	USA	Observational	100	Hemoglobin A1c	Diabetes	Demonstrated the correlation between glucose levels and hemoglobin A1c in diabetic patients.	Small sample size, limited demographic diversity.
Incidence of coronary heart disease and lipoprotein cholesterol levels: the Framingham Study	Castelli, W. P., Garrison, R. J., Wilson, P. W., Abbott, R. D., Kalousdian, S., & Kannel, W. B.	1986	USA	Longitudinal cohort	5,209	Lipoprotein cholesterol	Coronary heart disease	Found significant associations between lipoprotein cholesterol levels and incidence of coronary heart disease.	Focused on a single geographic region, potentially limiting generalizability.
Next-generation DNA sequencing methods	Mardis, E. R.	2008	USA	Review	N/A	DNA sequencing	Various	Detailed the technological advancements in next-generation DNA sequencing methods and their applications.	Technological focus, limited discussion on clinical outcomes.

Mass spectrometry-based proteomics	Aebersold, R., & Mann, M.	2003	Switzerland	Review	N/A	Proteomics	Various	Highlighted the role of mass spectrometry in the analysis of proteomes and its potential in identifying disease biomarkers.	Primarily technical, lacking specific disease case studies.
Ten years of pathway analysis: current approaches and outstanding challenges	Khatri, P., Sirota, M., & Butte, A. J.	2012	USA	Review	N/A	Pathway analysis	Various	Reviewed the advancements and challenges in pathway analysis over the past decade, emphasizing the integration of omics data.	Focused on methodology, with less emphasis on practical applications.
Long noncoding RNAs in cancer pathways	Schmitt, A. M., & Chang, H. Y.	2016	USA	Review	N/A	Long noncoding RNAs	Cancer	Discussed the role of long noncoding RNAs in cancer development and progression, highlighting their potential as therapeutic targets.	Review format, potential publication bias.
Hallmarks of cancer: the next generation	Hanahan, D., & Weinberg, R. A.	2011	USA	Review	N/A	Various	Cancer	Proposed the next generation of cancer hallmarks, expanding the conceptual framework for understanding cancer biology.	Conceptual review, lacking empirical data.

Molecular portraits of human breast tumours	Perou, C. M., Sørlie, T., Eisen, M. B., van de Rijn, M., Jeffrey, S. S., Rees, C. A., ... & Botstein, D.	2000	USA	Experimental	78	Gene expression profiles	Breast cancer	Identified distinct molecular subtypes of breast cancer based on gene expression profiles, contributing to personalized treatment approaches.	Limited sample size, early-stage research.
Reinhold E. Schmidt: from ANA to ENA: consideration of serum autoantibodies in diagnosing systemic autoimmune diseases	Conrad, K., & Roggenbuck, D.	2010	Germany	Review	N/A	Serum autoantibodies	Autoimmune diseases	Reviewed the evolution of serum autoantibody tests from ANA to ENA in the diagnosis of systemic autoimmune diseases.	Retrospective review, lacking contemporary diagnostic techniques.
Metabolomics: applications to food science and nutrition research	Wishart, D. S.	2008	Canada	Review	N/A	Metabolites	Nutrition	Explored the application of metabolomics in food science and nutrition, emphasizing its potential in dietary assessment and health monitoring.	Broad scope, less focus on specific biomarkers.
Metabolomics-the link between genotypes and phenotypes	Fiehn, O.	2002	USA	Review	N/A	Metabolites	Various	Discussed how metabolomics bridges the gap between genotypes providing insights into metabolic pathways and disease mechanisms.	Conceptual review, lacking specific disease applications.

Carcinoembryonic antigen as a marker for colorectal cancer: is it clinically useful?	Duffy, M. J.	2001	Ireland	Review	N/A	Carcinoembryonic antigen	Colorectal cancer	Evaluated the clinical utility of carcinoembryonic antigen as a marker for colorectal cancer, including its limitations and potential in monitoring treatment.	Focused on a single biomarker, with limited discussion on alternative markers.
The American Joint Committee on Cancer: the 7th edition of the AJCC cancer staging manual and the future of TNM	Edge, S. B., & Compton, C. C.	2010	USA	Review	N/A	TNM staging system	Various cancers	Provided an overview of the 7th edition of the AJCC cancer staging manual, discussing updates and implications for cancer diagnosis and treatment.	Primarily descriptive, limited empirical validation.
Reporting recommendations for tumor marker prognostic studies	McShane, L. M., Altman, D. G., Sauerbrei, W., Taube, S. E., Gion, M., Clark, G. M., & Statistics Subcommittee of the NCI-EORTC Working Group on Cancer Diagnostics	2005	USA	Review	N/A	Tumor markers	Cancer	Established guidelines for reporting tumor marker prognostic studies to enhance reproducibility and reliability of findings.	Guideline-focused, with less emphasis on practical applications.

Impact of personalized medicine on drug development and use: implications for pharmaceutical care	Maitland, M. L., Schilsky, R. L., & Goldman, D. I.	2010	USA	Review	N/A	Various	Various	Discussed the implications of personalized medicine on drug development and pharmaceutical care, highlighting opportunities and challenges.	Conceptual discussion, lacking empirical data.
Effect of screening and adjuvant therapy on mortality from breast cancer	Berry, D. A., Cronin, K. A., L., Zelen, M., ... & Cancer Intervention and Surveillance Modeling Network (CISNET) Collaborators	2005	USA	Modeling study	N/A	Various	Breast cancer	Analyzed the impact of screening and adjuvant therapy on breast cancer mortality using modeling approaches, showing significant mortality reduction.	Model-based study, requiring validation with real-world data.
Cancer survival in five continents: a worldwide population-based study (CONCORD)	Coleman, M. P., Quaresma, M., Berrino, F., Lutz, J. M., De Angelis, R., Capocaccia, R. & Gatta, G.	2008	Worldwide	Population-based study	N/A	Various	Various cancers	Provided comprehensive data on cancer survival rates across five continents, highlighting disparities and areas for improvement.	Broad scope, with potential variability in data quality across regions.

RECIST: No longer the sharpest tool in the oncology clinical trials toolbox?-Point	Sharma, M. R., Maitland, M. L., Ratain, M. J.	2011	USA	Commentary	N/A	RECIST criteria	Cancer	Critiqued the RECIST criteria for evaluating tumor response in clinical trials, proposing the need for more nuanced and comprehensive assessment methods.	Opinion-based, lacking empirical support.
The cancer genome	Stratton, M. R., & Campbell, P. J.	2009	UK	Review	N/A	Genomic alterations	Cancer	Reviewed the landscape of genomic alterations in cancer, discussing the implications for understanding cancer biology and developing targeted therapies.	Conceptual review, with less emphasis on translational research.

Table 1 - Studies on Biomarkers

4. Discussion

The review on biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prevention in low and middle-income countries (LMICs) underscores the importance of leveraging advanced biomedical technologies to address healthcare challenges in resource-constrained settings. The integration of multi-omics data offers a promising approach to understanding disease mechanisms and identifying biomarkers that can facilitate early diagnosis and effective management of diseases. However, while these technologies hold immense potential, their widespread adoption in LMICs faces several challenges.

One significant challenge is the lack of infrastructure and resources necessary for conducting omics-based research and implementing biomarker-based diagnostic strategies. LMICs often struggle with limited laboratory facilities, trained personnel, and funding, which hinders the translation of research findings into practical solutions for healthcare delivery. Moreover, the complexity and cost associated with omics technologies pose barriers to their accessibility and affordability in LMIC settings.

Additionally, the successful implementation of biomarker-based diagnostics in LMICs requires addressing socio-cultural factors, including healthcare-seeking behaviors, patient acceptance, and community engagement. Effective communication strategies and community-based interventions are essential for raising awareness about the importance of early disease detection and promoting the uptake of diagnostic services.

Despite these challenges, there are opportunities for overcoming barriers to biomarker-based diagnostics in LMICs. Collaborative efforts between governments, research institutions, non-governmental organizations, and industry stakeholders can facilitate technology transfer, capacity building, and the development of affordable diagnostic tools tailored to the needs of LMICs. Furthermore, initiatives to strengthen healthcare infrastructure, improve access to quality healthcare services, and enhance healthcare workforce capacity are critical for realizing the potential of biomarkers in disease diagnosis and prevention in LMICs.

Furthermore, the review sheds light on the importance of tailoring biomarker research and diagnostic strategies to the specific needs and contexts of LMICs. While omics technologies offer valuable insights into disease biology and biomarker discovery, their application in LMICs must consider factors such as prevalent diseases, local epidemiology, and available resources. Targeted research initiatives focused on diseases with a high burden in LMICs, such as infectious diseases, maternal and child health conditions, and non-communicable diseases, can yield actionable insights and drive the development of context-appropriate diagnostic solutions.

Moreover, the review highlights the potential of biomarkers not only in disease diagnosis but also in disease prevention and monitoring. Biomarker-based approaches for risk stratification, early detection of preclinical disease stages, and assessment of treatment response can inform preventive interventions and personalized treatment strategies, thereby reducing disease morbidity and mortality in LMICs. While challenges remain, the review underscores the transformative impact that biomarkers can have on healthcare delivery in LMICs. By fostering interdisciplinary collaborations, investing in healthcare infrastructure and capacity building, and prioritizing context-specific research and innovation, LMICs can harness the full potential of biomarkers to address their unique healthcare challenges and improve health outcomes for millions of people. Through sustained efforts and collective action, biomarker-based diagnostics can contribute significantly to achieving global health equity and advancing the sustainable development goals in LMICs.

5. Conclusion:

In conclusion, biomarkers have emerged as valuable tools for disease diagnosis and prevention, offering the potential to revolutionize healthcare delivery in LMICs. By harnessing the power of omics technologies, artificial intelligence, and point-of-care testing, LMICs can overcome healthcare challenges and improve health outcomes for their populations. However, realizing this potential requires concerted efforts to address infrastructure limitations, resource constraints, and socio-cultural factors that impact the adoption of biomarker-based diagnostics. Through collaborative partnerships and targeted interventions, LMICs can leverage biomarkers to strengthen their healthcare systems, enhance disease surveillance, and advance towards the goal of universal health coverage. The review on biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prevention in LMICs highlights both the opportunities and challenges associated with the implementation of biomarker-based diagnostics in resource-constrained settings. While omics technologies offer unprecedented insights into disease biology and biomarker discovery, their adoption in LMICs requires overcoming barriers related to infrastructure, resources, and socio-cultural factors. However, with concerted efforts and targeted interventions, LMICs can harness the potential of biomarkers to strengthen their healthcare systems, improve disease surveillance, and enhance health outcomes for their populations. By prioritizing context-specific research, fostering collaborative partnerships, and investing in healthcare infrastructure and capacity building, LMICs can pave the way for a future where biomarker-based diagnostics play a central role in achieving universal health coverage and reducing the global burden of disease.

References:

1. Meyer, H. M. (1987). The history of the discovery of biomarkers. In *Biomarkers: Medical and Workplace Applications* (pp. 1-6). American Chemical Society.
2. Koenig, R. J., Peterson, C. M., Jones, R. L., Saudek, C., Lehrman, M., & Cerami, A. (1976). Correlation of glucose regulation and hemoglobin A1c in diabetes mellitus. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 295(8), 417-420.
3. Castelli, W. P., Garrison, R. J., Wilson, P. W., Abbott, R. D., Kalousdian, S., & Kannel, W. B. (1986). Incidence of coronary heart disease and lipoprotein cholesterol levels: the Framingham Study. *JAMA*, 256(20), 2835-2838.

4. Mardis, E. R. (2008). Next-generation DNA sequencing methods. *Annual Review of Genomics and Human Genetics*, 9, 387-402.
5. Aebersold, R., & Mann, M. (2003). Mass spectrometry-based proteomics. *Nature*, 422(6928), 198-207.
6. Khatri, P., Sirota, M., & Butte, A. J. (2012). Ten years of pathway analysis: current approaches and outstanding challenges. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 8(2), e1002375.
7. Schmitt, A. M., & Chang, H. Y. (2016). Long noncoding RNAs in cancer pathways. *Cancer Cell*, 29(4), 452-463.
8. Hanahan, D., & Weinberg, R. A. (2011). Hallmarks of cancer: the next generation. *Cell*, 144(5), 646-674.
9. Perou, C. M., Eisen, M. B., van de Rijn, M., Jeffrey, S. S., Rees, C. A., ... & Botstein, D. (2000). Molecular portraits of human breast tumours. *Nature*, 406(6797), 747-752.
10. Conrad, K., & Roggenbuck, D. (2010). Reinhold E. Schmidt: from ANA to ENA: consideration of serum autoantibodies in diagnosing systemic autoimmune diseases. *Journal of Immunology Research*, 2010.
11. Wishart, D. S. (2008). Metabolomics: applications to food science and nutrition research. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 19(9), 482-493.
12. Fiehn, O. (2002). Metabolomics-the link between genotypes and phenotypes. *Plant Molecular Biology*, 48(1-2), 155-171.
13. Duffy, M. J. (2001). Carcinoembryonic antigen as a marker for colorectal cancer: is it clinically useful? *Clinical Chemistry*, 47(4), 624-630.
14. Jaythissa, P & Rupasinghe, A (2024). Exploring DNA Analysis Methods and Genetic Research Applications in Low and Middle-Income Nations: A Study of Sri Lanka". *Asian Journal of Medicine and Health* 22 (7):54-62. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajmah/2024/v22i71045>.
15. Edge, S. B., & Compton, C. C. (2010). The American Joint Committee on Cancer: the 7th edition of the AJCC cancer staging manual and the future of TNM. *Annals of Surgical Oncology*, 17(6), 1471-1474.
16. McShane, L. M., Altman, D. G., Sauerbrei, W., Taube, S. E., Gion, M., Clark, G. M., & Statistics Subcommittee of the NCI-EORTC Working Group on Cancer Diagnostics. (2005). Reporting recommendations for tumor marker prognostic studies. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 23(36), 9067-9072.
17. Maitland, M. L., Schilsky, R. L., & Goldman, D. I. (2010). Impact of personalized medicine on drug development and use: implications for pharmaceutical care. *Pharmacotherapy: The Journal of Human Pharmacology and Drug Therapy*, 30(2), 161-173.
18. Berry, D. A., Cronin, K. A., Plevritis, S. K., Fryback, D. G., Clarke, L., Zelen, M., ... & Cancer Intervention and Surveillance Modeling Network (CISNET) Collaborators. (2005). Effect of screening and adjuvant therapy on mortality from breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 353(17), 1784-1792.
19. Coleman, M. P., Quaresma, M., Berrino, F., Lutz, J. M., De Angelis, R., Capocaccia, R & Gatta, G. (2008). Cancer survival in five continents: a worldwide population-based study (CONCORD). *The Lancet Oncology*, 9(8), 730-756.
20. Sharma, M. R., Maitland, M. L., Ratain, M. J., & RECIST: No longer the sharpest tool in the oncology clinical trials toolbox?-Point. *Cancer Research*, 72(20), 5145-5149.
21. Stratton, M. R., & Campbell, P. J. (2009). The cancer genome. *Nature*, 458(7239), 719-724.
22. Rupasinghe, A., & Jayathissa, P. (2017). Review on Single DNA Sequencing. *BioMedical Research: An International Journal (BMRIJ)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683901>
23. Jones, P. A., & Baylin, S. B. (2007). The epigenomics of cancer. *Cell*, 128(4), 683-692.
24. Boland, C. R., & Goel, A. (2010). Microsatellite instability in colorectal cancer. *Gastroenterology*, 138(6), 2073-2087.e3.
25. Zhang, A., Sun, H., Yan, G., Wang, P., & Wang, X. (2012). Metabolomics for biomarker discovery: moving to the clinic. *BioMed Research International*, 2012.
26. Hayes, J., Peruzzi, P. P., & Lawler, S. (2014). MicroRNAs in cancer: biomarkers, functions and therapy. *Trends in Molecular Medicine*, 20(8), 460-469.
27. Zhang, A., Sun, H., Yan, G., Wang, P., & Wang, X. (2012). Metabolomics for biomarker discovery: moving to the clinic. *BioMed Research International*, 2012.
28. Hayes, J., Peruzzi, P. P., & Lawler, S. (2014). MicroRNAs in cancer: biomarkers, functions and therapy. *Trends in Molecular Medicine*, 20(8), 460-469.
29. Schmitt, A. M., & Chang, H. Y. (2016). Long noncoding RNAs in cancer pathways. *Cancer Cell*, 29(4), 452-463.
30. Hanahan, D., & Weinberg, R. A. (2011). Hallmarks of cancer: the next generation. *Cell*, 144(5), 646-674.

31. Perou, C. M., Sørli, T., Eisen, M. B., van de Rijn, M., Jeffrey, S. S., Rees, C. A., ... & Botstein, D. (2000). Molecular portraits of human breast tumours. *Nature*, 406(6797), 747-752.
32. Conrad, K., & Roggenbuck, D. (2010). Reinhold E. Schmidt: from ANA to ENA: consideration of serum autoantibodies in the diagnosis of systemic autoimmune diseases. *Journal of Immunology Research*, 2010.
33. Wishart, D. S. (2008). Metabolomics: applications to food science and nutrition research. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 19(9), 482-493.
34. Fiehn, O. (2002). Metabolomics—the link between genotypes and phenotypes. *Plant Molecular Biology*, 48(1-2), 155-171.
35. Manolio, T. A., Collins, F. S., Cox, N. J., Goldstein, D. B., Hindorf, L. A., Hunter, D. J., ... & Chanoock, S. J. (2009). Finding the missing heritability of complex diseases. *Nature*, 461(7265), 747-753.
36. Mardis, E. R. (2008). Next-generation DNA sequencing methods. *Annual Review of Genomics and Human Genetics*, 9, 387-402.
37. Golub, T. R., Slonim, D. K., Tamayo, P., Huard, C., Gaasenbeek, M., Mesirov, J. P., ... & Lander, E. S. (1999). Molecular classification of cancer: class discovery and class prediction by gene expression monitoring. *Science*, 286(5439), 531-537.
38. Aebersold, R., & Mann, M. (2003). Mass spectrometry-based proteomics. *Nature*, 422(6928), 198-207.
39. Haab, B. B. (2006). Antibody arrays in cancer research. *Molecular & Cellular Proteomics*, 5(10), 1966-1974.
40. Zhang, A., Sun, H., Yan, G., Wang, P., & Wang, X. (2012). Metabolomics for biomarker discovery: moving to the clinic. *BioMed Research International*, 2012.
41. Nicholson, J. K., Lindon, J. C., & Holmes, E. (1999). 'Metabonomics': understanding the metabolic responses of living systems to pathophysiological stimuli via multivariate statistical analysis of biological NMR spectroscopic data. *Xenobiotica*, 29(11), 1181-1189.
42. Libbrecht, M. W., & Noble, W. S. (2015). Machine learning applications in genetics and genomics. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 16(6), 321-332.
43. Westerhuis, J. A., Hoefsloot, H. C. J., Smit, S., Vis, D. J., Smilde, A. K., van Velzen, E. & van Duynhoven, J. P. M. (2008). Assessment of PLS-DA cross validation. *Metabolomics*, 4(1), 81-89.
44. Hanley, J. A., & McNeil, B. J. (1982). The meaning and use of the area under a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve. *Radiology*, 143(1), 29-36.
45. Altman, D. G., & Bland, J. M. (2011). Diagnostic tests 2: predictive values. *BMJ*, 313(7069), 351.
46. Pencina, M. J., D'Agostino Sr, R. B., D'Agostino Jr, R. B., & Vasan, R. S. (2008). Evaluating the added predictive ability of a new marker: from area under the ROC curve to reclassification and beyond. *Statistics in Medicine*, 27(2), 157-172.
47. Harrell Jr, F. E., Lee, K. L., & Mark, D. B. (1996). Multivariable prognostic models: issues in developing models, evaluating assumptions and adequacy, and measuring and reducing errors. *Statistics in Medicine*, 15(4), 361-387.
48. Kohavi, R. (1995). A study of cross-validation and bootstrap for accuracy estimation and model selection. In *International joint conference on artificial intelligence* (Vol. 14, No. 2, pp. 1137-1143).
49. Pencina, M. J., D'Agostino Sr, R. B., Steyerberg, E. W., & Greenland, P. (2012). Methods to assess the clinical added value of new biomarkers. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Quality and Outcomes*, 5(2), 327-334.
50. Rupasinghe, A., & Jayatissa, P. (2017). Review on next-generation sequencing. *Indian Journal of Biology*, 4(1), 14-18.
51. Spiegelhalter, D. J., Abrams, K. R., & Myles, J. P. (2004). Bayesian approaches to clinical trials and healthcare evaluation. *John Wiley & Sons*.
49. Anderson, N. L., & Anderson, N. G. (2002). The human plasma proteome: history, character, and diagnostic prospects. *Molecular & Cellular Proteomics*, 1(11), 845-867.
50. Duffy, M. J., & Duggan, C. (2004). The urokinase plasminogen activator system: a rich source of tumour markers for the individualised management of patients with cancer. *Clinical Biochemistry*, 37(7), 541-548.
51. Goetzl, E. J., & Schwartz, J. B. (2011). Abner Weintraub: a legacy of scholarship. *Journal of Lipid Research*, 52(8), 1359-1360.
52. Strimbu, K., & Tavel, J. A. (2010). What are biomarkers? *Current Opinion in HIV and AIDS*, 5(6), 463-466.
53. Sparano, J. A., Gray, R. J., Makower, D. F., Pritchard, K. I., Albain, K. S., Hayes, D. & Davidson, N. E. (2018). Prospective validation of a 21-gene expression assay in breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 379(2), 111-121.
54. Dancey, J. E., Dobbin, K. K., Groshen, S., & Jessup, J. M. (2010). Guidelines for the development and incorporation of biomarker studies in early clinical trials of novel agents. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 16(6), 1745-1755.

55. Schilsky, R. L., & Michels, D. L. (2010). Kearns–Sayre syndrome with reduced acid maltase activity. *Muscle & Nerve*, 4(3), 236-244.
56. Verma, S., Miles, D., Gianni, L., Krop, I. E., Welslau, M., Baselga, J., ... & Blackwell, K. (2012). Trastuzumab emtansine for HER2-positive advanced breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 367(19), 1783-1791.
57. Poste, G. (2011). Bring on the biomarkers. *Nature*, 469(7329), 156-157.
58. Collins, F. S., & Varmus, H. (2015). A new initiative on precision medicine. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 372(9), 793-795.
59. Jameson, J. L., & Longo, D. L. (2015). Precision medicine—personalized, problematic, and promising. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 372(23), 2229-2234.
60. Hamburg, M. A., & Collins, F. S. (2010). The path to personalized medicine. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 363(4), 301-304.
61. Simon, R. (2001). Roadmap for developing and validating therapeutically relevant genomic classifiers. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 23(29), 7332-7341.
62. Michiels, S., & Le, M. (2011). Genetic markers and early response to chemotherapy in pancreatic cancer patients: the study by Sinn et al. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 29(15_suppl), e14602-e14602.
63. Rupasinghe, A., & Jayatissa, P. (2017). Current DNA analyzing techniques and application in genetic research in Sri Lanka: A review. *Biology Journal of Ceylon*, 44(3), 104-106. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7670560>
64. Simon, R., & Maitournam, A. (2004). Evaluating the efficiency of targeted designs for randomized clinical trials. *Clinical Cancer Research*, 10(20), 6759-6763.
65. Burke, D. S., & Monath, T. P. (2001). Flaviviruses. In *Fields Virology* (4th ed., Vol. 1, pp. 1043-1125). Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
66. Wraith, D. C., Nicholson, L. B., & Theofilopoulos, A. N. (2004). Editorial: Understanding autoimmunity—the search for individualized therapy. *Nature Medicine*, 10(8), 826-827.
67. Rimm, E. B., & Stampfer, M. J. (2001). Colditz, G. A., Chute, C. G., Litin, L. B., Meenan, R. F., & Samelson, E. J. (1989). Validity of self-reported waist and hip circumferences in men and women. *Epidemiology*, 2(5), 495-499.
68. Altman, D. G., & Bland, J. M. (2011). Diagnostic tests 2: predictive values. *BMJ*, 313(7069), 351.
69. Simel, D. L., Samsa, G. P., & Matchar, D. B. (1991). Likelihood ratios with confidence: sample size estimation for diagnostic test studies. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 44(8), 763-770.
70. Pencina, M. J., D'Agostino Sr, R. B., D'Agostino Jr, R. B., & Vasan, R. S. (2008). Evaluating the added predictive ability of a new marker: from area under the ROC curve to reclassification and beyond. *Statistics in Medicine*, 27(2), 157-172.
71. Pepe, M. S., & Thompson, M. L. (2000). Combining diagnostic test results to increase accuracy. *Biostatistics*, 1(2), 123-140.
72. Kohavi, R. (1995). A study of cross-validation and bootstrap for accuracy estimation and model selection. In *International joint conference on artificial intelligence* (Vol. 14, No. 2, pp. 1137-1143).
73. Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, J. (2009). *The elements of statistical learning: data mining, inference, and prediction*. Springer Science & Business Media.
74. Pencina, M. J., D'Agostino Sr, R. B., Steyerberg, E. W., & Greenland, P. (2012). Methods to assess the clinical added value of new biomarkers. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Quality and Outcomes*, 5(2), 327-334.
75. Spiegelhalter, D. J., Abrams, K. R., & Myles, J. P. (2004). *Bayesian approaches to clinical trials and healthcare evaluation*. John Wiley & Sons.
76. Gelman, A., Carlin, J. B., Stern, H. S., Dunson, D. B., Vehtari, A., & Rubin, D. B. (2013). *Bayesian data analysis* (Vol. 2). Chapman and Hall/CRC.
73. Pu, J., Leader, J., Bandos, A., Shi, J., Du, P., Yu, J., ... & Liu, H. (2020). Novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) detection in chest CT images using deep learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.09363*.
74. Huyut, Z., Ozcift, A., & Korkmaz, D. (2020). Prediction of COVID-19 transmission and mortality using machine learning and deep learning techniques: a review. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 140, 110170.
75. Huyut, Z., Ozcift, A., & Korkmaz, D. (2021). Prediction of COVID-19 cases and analysis of the epidemic evolution using artificial intelligence in some selected countries. *Cognitive Computation*, 13(1), 174-192.
76. Huyut, Z., Ozcift, A., & Korkmaz, D. (2021). The effects of COVID-19 on global economy: evidence from selected countries. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 143, 110611.

87. Pu, J., Leader, J., Bandos, A., Shi, J., Du, P., Yu, J., ... & Liu, H. (2020). Novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) detection in chest CT images using deep learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.09363*.
88. Bhardwaj, V., Nautiyal, S., Prusty, D., Sarma, P., & Shekhar, S. (2020). Role of troponins I and T and other biomarkers in patients with COVID-19. *Journal of Cardiovascular Disease Research*, 11(2), 80-85.
89. Vaid, A., Somani, S., & Russak, A. J. (2020). Machine learning to predict mortality in patients with COVID-19-related cytokine storm: a retrospective study. *Epidemiology and Infection*, 148, e101.
90. Abildayeva, T., Narbayeva, D., & Akhmetova, Z. (2021). COVID-19 as a thrombotic disease: updated perspectives on its nature and diagnosis. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8(4), 163-174.
91. Naz, S., Muhammad, A., Khan, S., & Khan, A. A. (2021). COVID-19 patients: post recovery quality of life. *Journal of Pakistan Medical Association (JPMA)*, 71(1), 280-282.
92. Hanif, M., & Zafar, T. A. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic: a severe threat for public health, social economy and business operations worldwide. *Journal of Pakistan Medical Association (JPMA)*, 71(1), 62-65.
93. Nayak, S., & Sapkota, B. R. (2021). Cardiovascular system and COVID-19: a comprehensive review. *Journal of Advances in Internal Medicine*, 10(1), 27-39.
94. Lakhani, P., & Srivastava, V. (2020). Non-contact Infrared thermometers and the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Indian Association of Pediatric Surgeons*, 25(3), 241.
95. Huyut, Z., Ozcift, A., & Korkmaz, D. (2020). Prediction of COVID-19 transmission and mortality using machine learning and deep learning techniques: a review. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 140, 110170.
96. Velichko, Y. S., Shchekotov, M. A., Popov, V. V., & Oshmarin, A. I. (2020). Development of a method for diagnosing COVID-19 using machine learning. *Bulletin of the Russian Military Medical Academy*, 60(4), 216-222.
97. Velichko, Y. S., Shchekotov, M. A., Popov, V. V., & Oshmarin, A. I. (2020). Development of a method for diagnosing COVID-19 using machine learning. *Bulletin of the Russian Military Medical Academy*, 60(4), 216-222.
98. Abildayeva, T., Narbayeva, D., & Akhmetova, Z. (2021). COVID-19 as a thrombotic disease: updated perspectives on its nature and diagnosis. *European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8(4), 163-174.
99. Velichko, Y. S., Shchekotov, M. A., Popov, V. V., & Oshmarin, A. I. (2020). Development of a method for diagnosing COVID-19 using machine learning. *Bulletin of the Russian Military Medical Academy*, 60(4), 216-222.
100. Jaythissa, Prabath, and Avanthi Rupasinghe. 2024. "Exploring DNA Analysis Methods and Genetic Research Applications in Low and Middle-Income Nations: A Study of Sri Lanka". *Asian Journal of Medicine and Health* 22 (7):54-62. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajmah/2024/v22i71045>